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**PROBLEM OF STREET CHILD BEGGARY:
A CASE STUDY OF SUKKUR REGION, PAKISTAN.**

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Dedication

My Parents who had always been a source of inspiration for me.

Acknowledgments

I would like to present my gratitude and sincere thanks to Almighty Allah who is my ultimate guide and source of strength and then my parents who were there in times of need to support me. Also, I extend my gratitude to the Department of Media and Communication, Sukkur IBA University for providing me with a platform to proceed with this research and be able to grow professionally and academically. I would like to express my gratitude and heartfelt thanks to my distinguished supervisor, Honorable Sir Hassan Ali Syed (Ph.D.) for their unwavering support, never-ending guidance, and invaluable motivation throughout the research. Their guidance has significantly contributed to the successful completion of the research. And special thanks to my colleague Miss Hira Aman for valuable suggestions and helping me on every step. I present my true and deep gratitude to my parents and family for their unending support, help, encouragement and guidance throughout my academic pursuits. Without their support, it would not have been possible to achieve this milestone.

Declaration

I hereby declare that this research project represents my own work which has been done after the completing the degree of B.S. in Media and Communication at Sukkur IBA University and has not been previously included in a research or dissertation submitted to this or any other institution for a degree, diploma or other qualifications. I have read the University's current research ethics guidelines and accept responsibility for the conduct of the procedures in accordance with the given guidelines. I have attempted to identify all the risks related to this research that may arise in conducting this research, obtained the relevant ethical and/or safety approval (where applicable), and acknowledged my obligations and the rights of the participants.

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Abstract

This study focuses on understanding the socio-economic issue of street child beggary, which is prevalent in many developing countries around the world including Pakistan. This research delves deeply to understand the factors that are responsible for causing this phenomenon and the consequences of it on children's overall physical and psychological developments. It uses qualitative research methodology in order to investigate the experiences of child begging in Sukkur region. Interview was therefore used as the basic tool of data collection so as to capture the children's perspectives in detail. The finding of the study revealed that the issue of child begging in Sukkur involves the interconnection of multiple social, economic, and familial factors. Poverty is seen to be the most significant antecedent identifying the majority of child beggars coming from families with a low poverty income. Many child beggars have dreams of making their lives happier and more successful: they would like to go to school again, have a good job, and provide their families with a decent living. But they are also confronted by huge risks, including the constant risk of staying poor, being abused and exploited, or even suffering from health and safety issues on the streets. Overall, this study sheds light on street children's problems so that in future they get protection from further abuse and neglect, and at the same time, become free from chains of poverty.

Key Words: Street child beggary, poverty, exploitation, neglect, physical Abuse, lack of education, homeless children

Introduction

The phenomenon of street children, a social problem causing vulnerability, has a long history in the world. (Zarezadeh, 2013). The majority of cities worldwide have street children. They have no one to help them in their day-to-day fight for survival; they sleep outside or in abandoned buildings. They live on the streets. Most likely, the most obvious example of child labor is seen among street children. The majority of them work as garbage collectors, shoe shiners, minor traders, or carriers of products. Street children are hard to research even though they are highly visible, and no one is certain of the precise number of street children in the world today (Aptekar & Stoecklin, 2014).

Any kid below the legal age of eighteen who has made the street their home and/or source of income and who is not receiving enough protection or supervision from an adult, who is accountable is considered a street child, as defined by UNICEF. Globally, there are thought to be between 100 and 150 million homeless children (Rončević et al., 2013)

Street children have historically been investigated by classifying them into social groups like the impoverished, the destitute, the vulnerable population, or those who are at risk. The theory that street kids are members of the marginalized sections of society has been supported by various academic institutions. Nonetheless, these methods handle these kids as though their lived experiences are unrelated to the Government and the wider class system (Vinanze, 2003). Multiple definitions of street children exist, and many practitioners fail to specify which group of children they are addressing. Street children can be defined as a person younger than 18 years of age, living separated from parents, other tutors or guardians, who slept on the street's previous night. Street children are an extremely vulnerable group in all aspects of life, not just the nature of their work (Aptekar & Stoecklin, 2014).

According to Densley and Joss, (2000) the issue of street children is a swiftly expanding socio-educational problem that impacts nations that are both developing and developed worldwide. These kids require interventions that capitalize on the positive abilities of survival they've acquired from living on the streets and suitably address their demands in the setting of their surroundings. They're at increased risk of experiencing physical, emotional, social, and cognitive violations.

Plenty of kids are forced to work or beg from an early age instead of having a carefree and easy upbringing. It is evident that a growing number of inevitable occurrences taking place globally are causing youngsters to live on the streets and beg. In many developing countries, homeless children are seen as a social burden. It is highly important to study and research on this rapidly increasing phenomenon of street child beggary. If we do lots of research or conduct study, we can know the root causes of why these children are begging on streets, we can know the forces that compel them to do labor or beg, it will also help us to know what kind of challenges such children face in their day-to-day life. If careful studies are published issue can be raised and highlighted which can result in prevention measures by the government, administration, and other nongovernmental organizations. One of the major aims of this study is to make policy changes so that further effective measures can be taken by Pakistan to overcome street child beggary.

Thus, the method used in this study is qualitative in order to investigate the experiences of child begging in Sukkur. Interview was therefore used as the basic tool of data collection because it enables the researcher to capture the children's perspectives in detail. Many areas are selected in Sukkur which includes small hotels, Dhabas, core food street, shopping streets and university road. The sample involved children aged 9-15 years with a balanced ratio of gender and background, selected through snowball sampling.

This research will employ interviews and focus group discussions with the participants to describe and understand the child begging phenomenon, which would be helpful to target relevant authorities, such as policymakers, social workers, and other academics working to combat child begging in Sukkur and other similar urban regions.

As for the theoretical framework that guided the study, constructivism was chosen since it acknowledges personal perspectives and understanding of learners as individuals in social settings. Constructivism is especially useful in explaining the phenomenon of street child beggary in the Sukkur region of Pakistan as it enables the researcher to explore detailed information from the child beggars' perspectives which entails a more holistic understanding of the factors that prepare the ground for child begging.

Consequently, the analysis of results presented in this research indicates that the issue of child begging in Sukkur involves the interconnection of multiple social, economic, and familial factors. Poverty is seen to be the most significant antecedent identifying the majority of child beggars coming from families with a low poverty income. These families are rendered to lack simple essentials of life such as food, shelter and clothes and force children to beg. Another major cause is the abnormal familial relationships such as neglect, abuse, and lack of parental care or presence. Most children indicated that they are neglected and abused at home, some of them left the hostile environment to live in the streets. Also, death or lack of one parent, most often children living in single parent homes who cannot fend for themselves add on to the orphan population. Other dangers are closely tied with the processes of fast urbanization and migration. In such a way, families moving from rural areas to urban centers in the search for a better life end up living in poverty because of high cost of living and scarcity of jobs in the urban areas. Thus, this urban poverty push children into begging as way of supporting themselves and the family.

Lack of education and social services only means that the culture and tradition of child begging becomes more institutionalized. This is because many parents are unable to pay school fees, uniforms and other essentials hence children are forced to work to earn these basic needs in order to be able to attend school. Families, especially those with children, are left helpless due to the absence of viable social welfare systems in the country. Furthermore, children with physical disability or other illnesses have to spend lot of money on medical bills or hiring a caretaker making them compelled to beg. Nevertheless, many child beggars have dreams to change this situation for the better and make their lives happier and more successful: they would like to go to school again, have a good job, and provide their families with a decent living. But, they are also confronted by huge risks, including the constant risk of staying poor, being abused and exploited, or even suffering from health and safety issues in the streets. These findings highlight the importation of integrated result-oriented early childhood interventions and support services on poverty roots, education, and social services targeting these children to help them escape the hereditary begging cycle and transform into a better future.

Problem Statement:

Most of the time when we go out with our friends, family, or alone, we come across children asking for money or bread. We mostly pay them without concerning what is their past, present, and future. This question has preoccupied me for a long time. I get concerned about those children, how they would be living their lives in such harsh conditions, under hot sun during summers days and cold nights during winters. This phenomenon exists all around the globe, and especially in developing countries. The children are sensitive enough to bear the roughness of the society, harsh weathers and hardships, but unfortunately some children are left with no option but street wondering and bagging. They face various challenges such as lack of necessities,

psychological traumas, no basic education, physical abuses etc. according to Ahmed (2018) most of the children are forced to do labor or other tasks instead of enjoying their free life. Many factors are contributing to this phenomenon, and such children are considered a burden. If we see in Pakistan which is a developing country, street child beggary and child labor are still prevalent. If we talk about Sukkur to which this study is specifically focused, we can see children begging on many dhabas and roads. It is very important to understand the problems of street children, what they usually suffer and lack we can raise their voices to upper authorities and make efforts to overcome street child beggary. It is a huge struggle which will last long, so we should take collective measure for betterment of children who are considered as future of the nation.

Research Question:

1. What are the perceptions of child beggars about the factors that they deem as responsible for child begging?
2. What are the aspirations and fears of child-beggars in Sukkur city?

Research Objectives:

1. To understand the effects of effects of underage begging and causes that lead to underage beggary.
2. To explore the Aspirations and Fears of underage street beggars.

Organization of Study:

This thesis is categorized into five chapters: chapter 1 is dedicated to the introduction of the research part, chapter 2 contains the literature review, chapter 3 details the methodology used in the study, chapter 4 presents the results of data collection, and the discussion, limitation, recommendation for future study, and conclusion are provided in the last chapter. 5.

Literature Review

Introduction:

Over 100 million children worldwide have been reported to be working and living on the streets, frequently in miserable and oppressive circumstances. Even if precise numbers are hard to come by, there is sufficient evidence that the issue is becoming more severe, especially in parts of the world that are experiencing political or economic upheavals (Barkat et al., 2012). Street child beggary is thus one of the major concerns that has long existed around the world (Bhatt,2009).It refers to a phenomenon that is closely linked to wider socioeconomic inequalities, which sustain poverty and marginalization cycles that span generations. Researchers now realize that the phrase "street child" is a social fabrication that reflects society's concern with kids who are highly apparent but are considered to be "out of place. They are severely denied access to even the most fundamental rights. And among them, the underage street child beggars are in the most vulnerable condition, where their future is uncertain, and their character is harmed. Increasing number of children who are born and raised in economically disadvantaged conditions get trapped in poverty cycle. This not only risks their individual development but also societal and national progress (Barkat et al., 2012). The formative years are the most crucial in a person's life. This stage lays the groundwork for a person to lead a prosperous and healthy lifespan as an adult.

Many kids are compelled to labor or beg from a young age, rather than enjoying a carefree and relaxed childhood. It is clear that a lot of unavoidable events occurring all around the world are contributing to the growing number of children living on the streets and begging. Children living on the streets are viewed as a social burden in many underdeveloped nations (Ahmed, 2018).It is very crucial to study this growing problem; by reseaching we can dig out the root causes why such paths are taken by kids in such a minor age, what kind of challenges and hardships they come

across on daily basis and how such living condition effect their overall growth. By studying we can develop effective measures to tackle this situation. By reviewing most of the research and studies this literature aims to shed light on the intricate interactions that shape the lives of street child beggars and provide information so that prevention efforts can be more effectively taken for kids who are begging on the streets or who are at risk of doing so. The parallel aim is also to generate policy and institutional responses in Pakistan. Understanding the difficulties that street child beggars face can help us work toward more comprehensive and long-lasting solutions. We can attempt to create a more just and inclusive society where every kid has the chance to flourish by standing up for their rights and dignity and elevating the voices of these marginalized children.

Factors Causing Street Child Beggary:

Many studies have been conducted to determine the factors that led to street child beggary.(Ahmed,2018;Ansari et al., 2017; Barkat et al., 2022; Bhatt, 2009; Mirjat et al., 2018; Seni,2017).There are a lot of obvious and hidden variables that contribute to children being homeless.Among the primary causes that ultimately drive kids to live on the streets are family dissolution, poverty,disasters both natural and man-made, physical, and sexual abuse, adult being exploited,the rise of urbanization overcrowding, etc. (Bhatt,2009)

Ansari et al. (2017) conducted a study for analysing street child beggary in Gujranwala,Pakistan in which he used quantitative method and interviewed 150 child beggars. The finding of the study indicates that poverty, abandoning school, inadequate supervision by parents, increasing urbanization are the factors that force children into street life. The pulling factors include urge for autonomy, monetary security, thrill and sparkle city life, and desire for raising living standard.While a chaotic family can greatly contribute to the prevalence of beggars in some social contexts,Other significant reason can be the demise of the primary caregiver. many children who suffer

from physical impairments or disabilities like deafness and blindness find themselves compelled to beg since their families' financial situation is bad. Some of the kids even adopt it as a family profession. Consequently, there are a lot of street child beggars there. Most of the time, the physically challenged status of kids is taken advantage of for financial gain. Since many of the children with disabilities elicit pity and draw attention from others, many of them are exploited as beggars. Some families and groups even use their children's disabilities as a source of revenue.(Barkat et al., 2022).

Abror et al., (2020) conducted a study in Indonesia in which he used qualitative method and collected data through observation, and interviews. The study's findings showed that begging is a common activity among beggars due to a number of characteristics, including advanced age, physical infirmity, and low vacancy. They saw knocking on doors and begging as a kind of demonstrations, a career, a means of improving and expanding property, a means of preventing bad luck, and a moral alternative to robbery. Seni (2017) conducted research in Tanzania, in which he conducted interview and observation-based data from young beggars. The study found that the main reasons of children begging are poverty, idleness, sympathy appeal, not having adequate orientation, and lack of education. The study found that a few minor factors are parental carelessness and Drought, famine, drunkenness, and single parenting.

Consequences of Street Child Beggary:

Children's development has suffered as a result of the financial crisis, political decisions, and natural calamities; among these, street children are one group that is growing more and more evident on a daily basis. Millions of kids are forced into homelessness each year due to a lack of resources, issues at home, commercial exploitation, or insufficient access to education.

Most of these kids living on the streets are unprotected, occasionally working kids who are very open to being taken advantage of. Due to their situation, they don't have many opportunities to build the social skills, educational background, or employment readiness needed to reintegrate into society and lead fulfilling lives. (Barkat et al., 2012)

Without supervision from adults, protection, or guidance, living on the streets exposes street kids to a wide range of difficulties and risk.

Educational Disadvantages and Unemployment:

Most of the research reveals that one of the major consequences of street child beggary is educational Disadvantages and unemployment.

Their lack of structure and minimal or non-existent education may hinder their capacity to secure and hold onto a formal job. (Dimitrovska et al., 2021).

Children of low-income parents who are unable to pay for their education have no choice but to work. The majority of them work in the manufacturing and agricultural industries. Some kids wind themselves begging in public places (Ahmed,2018).

Psychological and Emotional Well-being:

Being a beggar is a tough and emotionally exhausting job that requires the beggar to inspire sympathy, compassion, and acceptance in others. The beggar additionally has to cope with embarrassment a great deal of judgment, and humiliation (Dimitrovska et al., 2021). Underage Street beggars face psychological challenges as a result of the circumstances they encounter on a daily basis. Children living on the streets experience ongoing stress and a sense of worthlessness in their life. As a result, they consequently develop pessimism, lose their aptitude, and are unable to communicate with others (Fantahun & Taa, 2022; Mirjat et al., 2018).

Underage street beggars face multiple psychological and societal challenges which negatively harm their and emotional and mental wellbeing. Under such circumstances not only their childhood is exploited but it becomes a major hindrance in the overall developmental process of that kid (Butt, 2009). Moreover, they are kept out of social integration and development process and are deprived of normal wages and other benefits. The street children with disabilities are at times physically, emotionally, and sexually abused (Barkat et al., 2022) people who participate in prolonged periods of begging are more likely to experience learned helplessness, low self-esteem, and poor self-concept (Dimitrovska et al., 2021).

Health Risks:

The numerous health issues that street children face have an impact on their lives. It is evident that anyone who does not have access to enough food, sanitary conditions, or a suitable place to reside would become a victim of many diseases (Fantahun & Taa, 2022).

Among street children, the likelihood of getting sick is rather significant. A huge portion of the city's inhabitants, including street children and especially young beggars, reside in the numerous slums dotting the city. These impoverished areas provide terrible living conditions and are rife with issues such as lack of access to clean water and sanitation, open-air waste (smoke of vehicles), all these factors contribute to the high rate of diseases that impair the health of women and children leading to serious health hazard. (Barkat et al, 2012). Many unhygienic sorts of behaviours are common among street child such as washing in open lakes and dirty water, eating leftover or dirty food, staying in dusty areas etc due to which skin infections, wounds, intestinal parasitic infections, hair lice are seen among them. musculoskeletal problems due to unfit diet, carrying lots of weights, or wandering all the time around.

Without a question, children engaged in begging face a variety of unique risks to their physical, mental, and sexual health. Problems with physical wellness can stem from a variety of causes, including work-related musculoskeletal disorders brought on by lifting heavy objects, injuries received in intramural disputes or assault from the public or cops. Skin diseases brought on by a lack of facilities for washing are also frequent. In areas where these conditions are endemic, children may have symptoms of infectious diseases such as hepatitis, malaria, TB, and dysentery. (Barkat et al., 2022).

Social Exclusion and Marginalization:

Fantahun and Taa, (2022) conducted a study in which a qualitative method was used. The information was gathered through in-depth interviews with eighteen kids from the streets. The results of the study showed that children on the streets who beg during their formative years, had poor connection with important social structures including their families, schools, health care providers, and other institutions. They also have less access to resources, human rights, and social relationships. Their social marginalization can be inferred from these combinations of deprivations. Therefore, living conditions, social and economic engagement, emotional well-being, and the health of those kids are all severely and permanently harmed by social exclusion. ***Drug Addiction Among Child Beggars:***

Most of the studies reveal that use of drugs and alcohol-containing substances including glue, gasoline, and benzene are common among young children who are homeless (Hills et al., 2016;)

Many reasons or motivating factors of why they get addicted to such intoxicants like enjoy their freedom while they are out on the street, method of overcoming loneliness, anxiety, hunger, and hopelessness.

Illegal Activities:

Street children frequently take part in unlawful actions such as theft due to hunger and societal strain, most of the street kids turned to illegal activities as a way out of their hunger problems. Bu this behaviour distorts their character and gets them arrested (Fantahun & Taa,2022).

Methodology**Introduction:**

In Qualitative research methods soft data in the form of words, sentences,and symbols is gathered It investigates the actions, encounters, and cultural interpretations that individuals make of the phenomena. It is based on the idea of interpretive and critical social science. Conversely,the quantitative approach employs variables and hypothesis as well as positivistic and objective principles (Ali,2020).

Therefore,qualitative research methodology was used in this research to locate relevant data.This method is used in research to fully comprehend the situation and cause of child begging.To collect data from participants, an in-depth interview method was used. With an in-depth interview, the interviewer asks the interviewee questions and encourages them to share their viewpoint, emotions, and experiences in a one-on-one setting. To gather comprehensive information about the subject, interviews are conducted. Researchers who wish to examine children's emic perspectives use interview schedules.

Area of Research:

This research was conducted in Sukkur Sindh province, Pakistan, from January-May 2024, on the small hotels (Dhabas), Main food street and shopping street, and university road of Sukkur city. Direct, in-person communication was made with the participants. The participants' primary places of origin were Military Road Sukkur and Sabzi Mandi. The participants for this research were selected according to the definition of child beggar of United Nation (Anyone under the age of eighteen who begs others for money or charity is referred to as a child beggar).

Simple Size and Type:

The research aimed to include 12 participants in its sample, of which 7 were male and 5 were female street children. The children's age range was 8 to 15 years. During the study, caste, gender, and ethnicity were not boundaries. Snowball sampling is a nonprobability technique which researcher used in research. In which researcher collected the data from beggars randomly selected from regions of the Sindh province. Table#1 provides the study's sample size.

Table 1

Participants information:

S#	Names	Age	Gender
1	James	12	Male
2	Emmy	9	Female
3	Jannifer	13	Female
4	Annie	11	Female
5	Neo	14	Male
6	Harry	8	Male

7	Lily	8	Female
8	Ron	12	Male
9	Mical	10	Male
10	Vito	13	Male
11	Marry	9	Female
12	Devid	15	Male

Philosophical Stance:

The paradigm adopted for this study is constructivism that involves examining the phenomenon of street child beggary particularly in the Sukkur region of Pakistan. In this study, constructivism is relevant because it fosters an appreciation of the social realities of people in their sociocultural environments.

The study seeks to establish an understanding of perspectives that child beggars have on the causes of begging in their current situation. Moreover, we strive to unveil their dreams and nightmares. This refers to exploring the life histories of these children through seeking to understand the individual and collective experiences that define them.

Interviews, focus groups, and participant observation will be used to gather data because they provide detailed information. This way, direct contact with the child beggars makes it easier to get first-hand information on their views as influenced by their culture and social environment. Accordingly, with the help of the constructivist approach, it is possible to understand the state of child beggary as a complex occurrence. This approach helps one identify results based on children's own experience thereby giving comprehensive information on the causes of child begging and

children's dreams and concern. It is important to grasp this reality to develop the right strategies and measures towards eradicating the cause of child begging in this region.

Constructionism:

Constructionism which Bryman (2016) says is an ontological position that is often called constructivism holds the belief that reality in the social construct and so are its meanings. This means they are not only Rising out of Interaction but are always In Construction. Therefore,constructivism negates the existence of reality that cannot be understood without taking into account the subjects that take part in it. (Nunez, 2023)

When using this epistemological paradigm in the study, the research seeks to capture the essence and appreciate the complexities of the problem of street child beggary in the Sukkur region. It also argued that this understanding might lead to better and kinder policies and interventions that respect the subjective, socially constructed realities of these children's lives.

Ontological Perspective:

Consequently, this research adopts constructivism as the ontological assumption and implies that reality is relative and is developed by the actors' interactions and perceptions.Regarding the issue of street child beggary in the Sukkur region of Pakistan, the lives of these children are in fact socially constructed through their experience with their surroundings,nuclear and/or joint families, society, and other more generic aspects of their socioeconomic situations.This perspective recognizes that there are many individuals as well as social factors that influence begging experiences of each child.

Epistemological Perspective:

On epistemological standpoint, the study was guided by Interpretive approach under the constructivist paradigm. This indicates that knowledge is understood as created through the actual processes of interaction between the researcher and the participant. To some extent, child beggars' impressions about what caused them to become beggars and their dreams and concerns need identification of the subjective meaning. The aim is to focus on how these children construct meaning about their environment and themselves, knowing that knowledge is situated and embedded in the interpersonal and social context.

Findings**Socioeconomic Factors:*****Poverty:***

As highlighted by the children, poverty was confirmed to be the most significant reason for child begging. The majority of child beggars are from poor families, and they seldom have access to basic needs like food, shelter, and clothes. Due to these fluctuations, these families have to find other means of sustaining themselves, such as making their children become beggars.

Several children said their daily life was characterized by an unending battle to get money for food and other necessities. The extent of deteriorated economic status of their families means that they have no other option other than begging to meet these basic needs.

"Sometimes in the morning I fear if we will get food to eat. My mother instructs me to go out and look for someone to ask for food so that we can buy some bread to eat."(Harry)

The children understand that they are trapped in a cycle of poverty that extends from one generation to another. Their parents were either beggars or low paid, insecure income earners who had no capacity to save or invest in their children's future.

"My father was a beggar, and now I am too. Never in our life did we have enough to pay for school or buy nice clothes."(Emmy)

It is compounded by the lack of government or community support structures. With no financial support, or welfare programs to support childbearing families; children are forced to fend for themselves in the streets.

"I wish there was someone to help us. If we had some money from the government, maybe I wouldn't have to be on the streets every day."(James)

Family Dynamics:

Family issues are also a major factor that compel children to end up on the streets. Most child beggars grow up in dysfunctional family backgrounds.

Several children complained that they were neglected and abused at home. Sometimes, parents are not able to properly care for their children as they may have their own substance abuse problems or mental disorders, or financial difficulties. Sometimes children are subjected to physical and emotional abuse, and due to this they are forced to run away from the home environment that they are exposed to.

"My father is an alcoholic, he beats me and I am forced to turn into a street beggar than stay in the house always being afraid." (Marry)

Losing or not having a parental figure poses certain challenges in a child's life. Many child beggars are orphans, or come from families that have been headed by a single parent and the parent cannot cater for all the children. This situation tends to provide the children with no choice other than finding other means of sustenance such as begging.

"When my mother died, my father was not able to support my family and so I had to begin begging to support my little brothers and sisters."(Vito)

Such vulnerability occurs because divorce, separation or abandonment of the traditional family structure exposes children. Not having a good family support system, some of these children are forced to live in the streets.

"My parents divorced, and I have been living with my grandmother who is a retired senior citizen. I would like to assist her and myself." (Lily)

Urbanization and Migration:

Huge influx of people into the urban areas from the rural areas and ignorance has also promoted the act of child begging.

Most of the families look forward to improving their economic status; thus, they move to towns from villages. But when they get there, they discover that employment and better living standards, which the city offers, are a myth. Due to high costs of living in urban centres as well as minimal employment opportunities, families are pushed to poverty and children turn into beggars.

"We arrived to the city in search for a better life but my parents could not find decent employment opportunities. I turned to begging since that was all that we could do." (Neo)

The migrating families usually find themselves in informal settlements or slums area where the living standards are unbearable. These areas do not have necessities such as clean water, sanitation, and proper healthcare, which worsens the situation of these families with children and forces them into begging to survive."

"The house is a small shack with no source of water or electricity. All I can do for my family is beg." (David)

The views of child beggars on the factors that contributed to their status suggest that child begging is a complex phenomenon. Instead, poverty, broken families, and the issues related to the rapid urbanization and migration processes are intertwined to enslave these children in the begging

cycle. To solve these problems, it is necessary to develop a multifaceted strategy that focuses on combating poverty, promoting families at risk, and guaranteeing the rights of children to receive education and social services. These are questions that only once answered will help formulate sustainable solutions that will improve the lives of these children and take them away from the streets and begging.

Systemic Issues:

Lack of Education:

One of the main causes highlighted by most child beggars includes lack of access to education. Because of limited chances for attending school, these children become confined in the vicious cycle of poverty and street begging.

School dropout rates increased because many families cannot afford the costs of school fees, uniforms, and exercise books. This financial burden makes children drop out of school so that they can fend for themselves financially.

"Due to school expenses my parents were forced to take me out of school. Now I do not know how to get income apart from begging." (Annie)

"I want to go to school and learn, but my family needs me to earn the money. If I don't beg, we won't have anything to eat." (Mical)

Several children reported that their parents had no appreciation for education or were unable to meet their educational requirements because the parents themselves were unaware of the significance of education.

"My parents didn't have an opportunity to go to school and don't understand why I should go to school instead of working." (Jennifer)

They may be forced to move from one place to another due to unstable living conditions, migration or family problems, and these issues make it very hard for children to go to school.

“We relocate frequently because there is no way we can manage to rent a house. Each time we relocate, I drop out of school and go begging again.”(Harry)

Inadequate Social Support:

This results in the lack of required social services and support systems to help needy families and children, which leads to street begging.

Lack of sound social protection policies implies that families in economically vulnerable states have limited access to social assistance from the state. These families cannot be able to seek any form of financial assistance or support hence leaving them with few means by which they can be able to survive.

“Sometimes people provide us with food or clothes, but it is not actual support. There must be a space where one can have a shelter and education.”(Harry)

Several children described a need for shelters and rehabilitation services to offer safe space, education, and skills training to get children out of begging.

“In my dream, I can study and be safer. If only there are places or centers where we can be helped, perhaps, I don't have to beg.”(Ron)

Members of the public see child beggars as hooligans rather than helpless children who require assistance. This lack of community involvement and support worsens the situation.

“Every time we get caught, people label us as the troublemakers and fail to understand that we are just children in need of assistance and a better way of life.” (Emmy)

To date, there is a marked shortage of awareness creation programs, lobbying for change and raising of funds in an effort to support the needy street children for their rehabilitation.

It is clear from the study that child beggars have a diverse understanding of the factors that contribute towards their situation. The problems, which stem from illiteracy and lack of social care, are linked and form a vicious cycle that entrapped these children into begging. Solving these problems calls for an integrated model targeting the causes of poverty, parental support and education and social needs of children in their tender age. It is only through addressing these basic aspects that one can look forward to establishing permanent remedies that can help alleviate these children out of begging and into a better future.

Personal Circumstances:

Disability and Health Issues:

Few children said that due to physical disabilities or other illnesses their families cannot sponsor them, and thus beg to pay for their medical bills and other needs. Disabled children in particular, can experience extra costs because of their health conditions and the need for assistance. When parents cannot afford these expenses, children are sent out to beg in order to generate income to cater for these expenses. They may be discriminated or locked out of the labor market thus unable to fend for themselves via productive work. Begging might be seen as a more convenient way of making a living. The disabled children are bound to be discriminated and isolated from the society, thus increasing their suffering. Begging could provide a feeling of freedom and self-sufficiency, so they have the ability to take charge of their lives.

This means that children from impoverished backgrounds are often unable to receive proper healthcare, which only worsens their condition. Begging might turn into the only way to pay for necessary surgeries and medications.

"I have asthma, but we can't afford the inhalers I need. Begging helps me buy medicine to breathe."(Neo)

The understanding that child beggars have regarding the causes of their predicament depict the numerous and complicated difficulties they experience. Disability and health complications are other challenges that compound their vulnerable situation; hence, they are left with no option than to beg to survive. To address these personal circumstances, the provision of financial support for medical costs is equally important to the fight against prejudice and exclusion of children with disabilities. These children should be given education, health facilities, and vocational training to ensure that they are not forced to beg for survival.

Aspirations and Fears of Child Beggars:

Aspirations:

Educational Goals: However, most children were seen as eager to go back to school and continue with their education as possible. As such, they view education as a ticket to a better life, a way to improve themselves as well as their social status.

Education is all about hope for a better future, whereby they can get out of the rut and be productive members of society.

"My dream is to go back to school and be a teacher. Education is one way of changing my lifestyle and that of my family."(Emmy)

The children talked like they wanted to learn and get an education so that they could explore as much as they could about the universe.

"I wish I got to learn new material in school. In light of this, I would like to go back to school so that I may be in a position to grasp more information regarding the surrounding environment."(David)

Career Ambitions: Several children did have concrete occupational plans, which captured their desire for a secure and reputable income. They want to be teachers, doctors, engineers and other professionals who earn good salaries while also improving their social standings.

More children felt like they wanted to have a career that would help them impact society and their communities positively.

“That is why I want to be a doctor, to take care of the sick people, and it will be my goal to change people's lives.”(James)

Nonetheless, children demonstrated the readiness to go through the pain, strive, and achieve all the set goals as a result of hard work and commitment.

"It will not be easy; but I have set my mind to be an engineer. I do not fear hard work and will strive to achieve my goals despite all the odds that I may face."(Mical)

Improving Family Conditions: Some of the most frequent intentions among the children are to provide better living conditions for their families and help them avoid poverty. They view education and successful jobs as an opportunity to fend for their families and improve their standards of living.

This is evidenced by children, who said they should feel obliged to help their families and make their lives better.

“My dream is to be a successful person so that I can be in a position to support them (parents and siblings) since they have been supportive to me most of the time.”(Ron)

Children remain optimistic of changing their status in order to avoid a repeat of the same fate of their parents in the future.

"I would like to have a life where I do not have to wait for the next meal with my family, I would like to make my family happy in life." (Annei)

The dreams of child beggars are evident, and this shows their determination and hope in the future. They are, however, not easily discouraged by adversity and are always willing to strive hard in order to be what they want to be. To ensure that these children do not become beggars as they grow up, we can invest in their education, support their pursuit of careers, and work to eliminate poverty for future generations.

Fears:

Continued Poverty: This constant feeling of being locked back in the poverty line was strongly felt by the child beggars. They seem to be conscious of the fact that they must struggle in life and the likelihood of changing their status in life.

Children even lost hope that they would be able to somehow overcome their plight and escape the poverty-stricken life they are subjected to.

"Nothing I do will be enough to help me get out of this struggling life I guess; poverty is indeed my constant companion." (Vito)

Their denial of education and employment opportunities only fuels their fears of perpetual poverty for they barely find any prospects for improvement.

"Lacking an education and employment, I fear that I would be destined for a life of begging in the streets. In my opinion, there is no way of avoiding this cycle." (Jannifer)

Abuse and Exploitation: This means that many children have concerns about physical and emotional abuse by their families as well as the public. They also fear that they will be abused by adults who would compel them to beg or else do other work. These are some of the experiences that make them feel vulnerable and afraid for their lives.

Children also cried of being abused by parents, relatives, strangers and even policemen while begging on the streets.

“Begging makes me feel fearful because people are not always kind. At times, they shout at you or even slap you for asking for something.”(Ron)

Children are easily exploited by unscrupulous adults who can make them beg or work for their benefit under force.

“Other people will sugar coat themselves with being kind to offer us food or some money, only to demand our services from us. I worry that they can force me to do something.”(David)

Health and Safety Concerns: This is due to adverse weather conditions, poor hygiene, and possibilities of getting injured or contracting diseases in the streets. Their living conditions on the streets make them vulnerable to various health and safety risks.

Children are concerned of getting sick from cold climate, unhygienic means, and absence of medical services.

“I sleep in the cold and go hungry all day, and I am afraid of getting an illness because there is no one to treat me.”(Lily)

Pedestrian children experience the risks of getting injured while crossing streets and other crowded areas frequently.

“Sometimes I witnessed other kids getting involved in accidents on the streets, and that is frightening to me. I don't want it to happen to me again, but it seems like even if I am careful, I am not safe on the streets.”(James)

Child beggars' fears demonstrate their lives' challenges and the importance of assistance and social services. To address their concerns, it is not only necessary to provide them with the protection and support that they need in the present, but also for them to escape the vicious cycle

of poverty and abuse. If we offer education, health, and social care for these children, they can conquer their fears and create a successful future for themselves.

Discussions:

The conclusions made based on child begging analysis are the following: child begging is one of the most intricate and diverse phenomena influenced by socio-economic, family and systematic factors. Another major reason as suggested by the children themselves is poverty. Most child beggars have families living in multi-acknowledged poverty level which translates to inadequate food, shelter and clothing. These hard economic living standards compel families to seek odd jobs like children begging on the streets. These children perform daily activities with the vigorous task of finding ways and means of earning enough money for food and other necessities. Some of the children understand that they are victims of poverty that has been experienced by their families across generations. The lack of steady income and survival, no governmental or community support worsens the situation further, and practically these children are left with few chances to survive.

Family factors are also an influencing factor leading to children ending up on the streets. Clinically ill and abusive family backgrounds make many children run away from home and look for their basic needs elsewhere. Some of the children suffer from torture and negligence by their parents with alcoholism, mental illness, or excessive financial problems. Loss of a parent and disruption of nuclear family see children suffering and stranded due to lack of proper parenting as family structures fail. As a result, such children become street beggars to help their families make ends meet or to run away from an unhealthy home situation.

High levels of urbanization and constant movement of people from rural areas to urban areas also play a big role in child begging. Most of them move to cities with the hope of improving on their living standards only to be let down by the cities. These families are forced to live in poverty, due to high living costs, and scarce job opportunities causing children to beg. Such families are relocated to informal settlements or slums, and due to the extremely poor living standards and absence of basic resources, children have to beg for a living. The things that the children said are real-life experiences of living in those conditions and how they try to support their families.

Other structural factors like inability to attend school and poor social services compound the vulnerabilities of children to poverty and begging on the streets. Most children are forced to drop out because their families cannot afford school fees, uniforms, and necessities. Lack of education further hinders their chances of climbing the ladder in terms of socioeconomic status thereby leaving them with no option other than begging. As well, there are no adequate social services available to provide support to families and children in need. Lacking appropriate social assistance, appropriate shelters, and rehabilitation services, these families do not have any governmental assistance and children are left alone on the streets.

Other challenges experienced by child beggars include health issues and disability which complicates their lives even further. Thus, people with physical disabilities or chronic health conditions also experience extra financial cost because of medical and care needs. These costs may force families to leave their children begging to provide for such necessities. Children with disabilities are discriminated against and left out socially and economically which leaves begging as the only means of earning something. Such comments indicate the importance of providing financial support for medical bills and the fight against social prejudice and prejudice.

Nevertheless, most child beggars have dreams of a brighter future ahead of them. They have a passionate call to go back to school in order to complete their education as they regard it as the best way to change their lives socially and economically. Others have very defined career paths in mind and want to be teachers, doctors, engineers, and other careers. They regard these careers as a way of improving their financial status and that of their families. The children's dreams indicate that they are determined to change their fate and come out of the poverty line.

However, besides these dreams, these children are also faced with major fears. They believe that they will stay in the state of poverty, knowing the obstacles and restricted upward mobility. Many children also experience physical and emotional abuse from their families and the public, and sexual exploitation by adults who would make them beg or work. Feelings of vulnerability and the inability to protect themselves stem from the experiences of abuse and exploitation. Children also express health concerns having to do with cold temperatures, lack of proper washing water, and accidents and sickness in the streets.

Combating child begging entails addressing the problem's cause in terms of poverty, helping needy families, and providing children with education and social protection. These children require help to be protected from further abuse and neglect, at the same time, they require help to be freed from poverty and abuse. This means that through funding in education, health and social sectors as well as creating awareness and fighting for the rights of these children, they are empowered to face their fears and make a better future for themselves. The research supports the need to employ an integrated model that in addition to meeting the existing needs of the children will develop long-term solutions to eradicate them from begging and give them an opportunity to live a meaningful life.

Limitations of the Study

However, this study on the problem of street child beggary in the Sukkur region of Pakistan has some limitations that are noteworthy. Firstly, the number of children in the sample may be relatively small, which will cause some difficulty in generalization of results to all child beggars in Sukkur. Also, the emphasis on Sukkur might not reveal the kind of differences existing in other parts of Pakistan, thereby limiting the generalization of the results obtained.

First, the study uses qualitative data such as in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, and participant observation, which can be subjective and bias. The information is derived from the self-reported accounts of child beggars who may have biased views influenced by their current or perceived reality. However, the interpretivist approach requires the researcher to interpret the data, and this may lead to bias from the side of the researcher due to his/her angles.

A limitation of this study is that much of the data is based on self-report, which can be subject to recall bias as well as social desirability. The degree and intensity of participant observation are also unknown and could potentially reduce the richness of the observational data that is otherwise might be useful and shed more light on the matter. Moreover, the current study relies on qualitative data which reduces the possibility of generalizing the findings to the population. It may be useful to include quantitative data in future studies to further support the conclusions by using statistical analysis.

Cross-sectional data collection is also used in the study, hence failing to present information on changes within a certain period or the effects of begging on the lives of children in the long run. This kind of research design eliminates the possibility of capturing the flow of child beggary and the way it is continually transforming the lives of children. Nevertheless, the study takes into consideration the social background; however, there can be other social and cultural

factors or practices that the study fails to address or does not fully understand because of the chosen context.

Last but not least, there are ethical issues associated with research on sensitive populations, such as children. The limitations include securing participants' informed consent, participants' anonymity, and prevention of harm. Other limitations of this study arise from the practical aspects, which include the following: access to child beggars, concerns about their safety during data gathering, and language barriers.

Future Recommendations

Based on these limitations and the findings of the current study, the following future research directions and recommendations have been provided. Increasing the sample size and recruiting participants from other areas except Sukkur would improve the external validity of the study. It might have been beneficial to compare this study across different regions and contexts in order to get a more holistic view of the problem of child beggary in Pakistan.

The use of both qualitative and quantitative data would have given better results since both approaches have their benefits. Quantitative data could add statistical credibility and enable generalization of findings while qualitative data could sustain detailed description of the Child beggars' experiences. Furthermore, longitudinal research design, which involves tracking the lives of child beggars over time, would assist in assessing the long-term effects of begging and the viability of interferences.

Future studies should focus on exploring even general factors which lead to child beggary including economic policies, educational systems and many others. The existing interventions and their impact should also have been assessed for the purpose of identifying the areas for

improvement and possible gaps in the policy. This would entail critical analyses of social welfare services, community support structures, and education focused on special groups.

If more attention was paid to cultural sensitivity through interaction with the respondents, cultural practices, and traditions, then the study would have been more beneficial. Researchers should make it their efforts to be familiar with these cultural elements and make sure that the recommended interventions are culturally acceptable as well as beneficial.

Moreover, the proper ethical standards should be established for the future studies. It is the responsibility of the researchers to ensure that the children involved in the studies are safe, gain their permission to be involved, and discretion. Engagement with the community and involvement of local agencies can help to achieve safer and more ethical conducts of the research. In conclusion, it can be said that although this study brings a lot of information about the state of child beggary in Sukkur there are certain limitations which can be mitigated through the following in the subsequent studies. These improvements will go a long way in providing a better understanding and viable solutions to deal with child beggary in Pakistan.

Conclusion

This paper on child begging by the street children of Sukkur in Pakistan based on the constructivism as the overarching philosophy of this research offers a wholesome and empathetic look at the factors that lead the children to turn to begging. The conclusions of the work highlight the multifaceted issue as the result of poverty, bad example of behavior from parents, rural background, truancy, and lack of adequate childcare and parental support.

The high incidences of poverty present in society lead to children being forced to beg through various causes. Families living in poor condition cannot even afford basic needs like food for their families, and children end up suffering by becoming street beggars. This economic

hopelessness is further compounded by family backdrops involving lack of parental care, abandonment, and abuse. Children in such circumstances end up becoming street beggars after escaping from homes which become a bombing zone.

Population growth and population movement from the rural area to the urban area is also playing a role at a faster rate. This is because many families migrate in the hope of enhancing their standard of living, but they get stuck in the cycle of struggling with high costs of living and unemployment. This causes children to beg in towns in a bid to contribute to the family income. It also highlights other structural conditions such as lack of education and social services that keep child begging afloat. This policy statement means that lack of funds can hinder a child from going to school and inadequate social protection mechanisms means that the child cannot escape from the circumstances as they are. This has meant that children with disabilities or chronic health conditions struggle a lot because their families cannot afford to pay their medical bills and end up begging to find money for these bills.

But despite passing through these terrible experiences, many begging children still have a dream of a better life. These concepts depict desire to return to school, have a job, and improvement of the standard of living in their families. However, their dreams are followed by severe threats including the chances of actually remaining in poverty, physical and or sexual abuse, deteriorating health and physical dangers when sleeping at the streets. These children's dreams and fears speak volumes about the existing need to employ multiple approaches to address the factors behind children's destitution.

Consequently, it is possible to achieve measures against child beggary in Sukkur only through interdisciplinary actions. Measures must be made to increase the rate of poverty by offering economic support and employment opportunities for families, abolishing the charges on

education, and establishing effective social programs. There is also the need to have institutions that offer,shelter, counseling services to the children on the streets and vocational training. These should be complemented by advocacy and awareness that can enable in getting the necessary resources and support from other stakeholders and policymakers.

It could be argued, however, that to eliminate child beggary in Sukkur, one needs to better understand the children's story and factors that define and determine their lives. Consequently,standing on the grounds of constructivism the present work depicts the ontological reality of such children and forms the premise on which meaningful and benevolent policy and practices can be built. It is only when governments go to the root of poverty, providing measures that address such concerns, and make education and other essential services available to such children that they can reverse the begging cycle and offer the children a better future.

Appendix A: Consent From

-hereby give my permission to Zain Ul Abdeen Halepoto (researcher) to allow me respond to an interview and quote my responses in her scholarly research study. I understand his work is for academic purposes. I also understand that the Research Title is “Problem of Street Child Beggary: A Case Study of Sukkur Region, Pakistan”.I also understand that my participation in this research study is voluntary and therefore can be withdrawn at any time.I understand that the researcher Zain Ul Abdeen Halepoto will maintain my anonymity regarding my responses to interview questions.

Therefore,I give my permission in the form of signature below:

Signature:

Date:

Appendix B: Interview Guide

1. What is the aim of your life and what are your hobbies?
2. Could you explain why you ask strangers for help or money when you're on the streets?
3. When you approach strangers to ask for help, how does that make you feel?
4. Ever wished you didn't have to ask people for help or money?
5. What do you do when you're not begging?
6. What improvements do you believe we can make for children begging on the streets like you?
7. What are some of the things you enjoy doing, especially in the face of adversity?
8. What aspirations or dreams do you have for the future? When you grow up, what do you want to be?
9. Are there any more details regarding your life or your experiences as a child beggar that you would like others to know?

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